

OCEAN:ICE

Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in ANtarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth system

SCOPE

The largest block of ice on Earth, the Antarctic Ice Sheet, covers more than 14 million square kilometres. Melting of even a fraction of the ice sheet has the potential to cause catastrophic sea level rise, but there are huge holes in our understanding of the processes and ocean feedbacks driving ice sheet melt, that lead to uncertainties of up to 1.5 m in projections of sea level rise by 2100, or over 10 m by 2300. The EU and UKRI funded OCEAN:ICE project brings together 17 European research centres and numerous international collaborators to improve assessments of sea level rise and the impact on the European and global climate from the melting ice sheets. It will make new ocean and ice sheet observations and develop coupled ice sheet-climate models that can be used to predict how changes in the Antarctic and Greenland ice sheets impact global climate. On the basis of new and existing data, the project will reduce uncertainty in estimates of ice sheet melt, sea level rise and the impact and feedbacks of ocean circulation.

OBJECTIVES/MISSION

OCEAN:ICE seeks to understand the impacts of polar (mainly Antarctic) ice sheet and Southern Ocean processes on Planet Earth, via their influence on sea level rise, deep water formation, ocean circulation and climate. It combines new and novel observations around the Antarctic Ice Sheet and Southern Ocean with cutting edge modelling and model development; crucially including improving and running coupled ice sheet-climate models to observe the role of feedbacks between the cryosphere and ocean on global climate to 2300 and beyond. New observations, including campaigns beneath 'warm' and 'cold' ice shelves, and existing observations will be assimilated into improved ice sheet boundary conditions and forcing. These will be used to produce new estimates of recent past and present ice sheet melt (including Greenland). These improved ice sheet models will be used alongside rigorous numerical approaches to constraining uncertainty in future ice sheet surface runoff, basal melt and iceberg calving under various forcing scenarios and comparing coupled with uncoupled ice sheet-ocean interactions. They will also assess the 'deep uncertainty' associated with processes such as marine ice cliff instability to constrain future estimate of sea level rise. OCEAN:ICE will then use these fluxes to assess impacts on ocean circulation, including the Atlantic Meridional Overturning circulation, global climate and feedbacks to the ice sheets. Finally, it will establish the potential for passing ice sheet 'tipping points' in the coming centuries and their consequences, including 'tipping cascades', out to millennial time scales.

OCEAN:ICE overview schematic of work package themes

Finally, OCEAN:ICE will directly contribute to the All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance through observations, logistical collaboration and analysis and will involve a wide network of international collaborators from South African, South Korea, Argentina, Brazil, Australia, Germany, Japan and New Zealand. It will significantly advance the state-of-the-art in coupled ice sheet-climate modelling and directly contribute to model intercomparison projects and international climate assessments such as the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change and World Ocean Assessment. It will link organically to European data centres to disseminate its data, following FAIR and INSPIRE principles and will deliver improved assessments of European climate impacts from the melting ice sheets, with actionable risk and timescales, to policymakers and the public. OCEAN:ICE will also champion EDI principles and provides funding for the Women in Polar Science network.

CONTACT DETAILS

For further information on OCEAN:ICE please see <https://www.ocean-ice.eu/> or contact Ruth Mottram (rum@dmi.dk) and Andrew Meijers (andmei@bas.ac.uk)

Project details	
Budget	4 886 890 (4 886 890 EU Contribution)
Duration	1 November 2022- 31 October 2026
Call	HORIZON-CL6-2021-CLIMATE-01
Type of Action	RIA
Website	www.ocean-ice.eu
Social media	https://twitter.com/OCEANICE_EU https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU https://www.facebook.com/OCEANICEEU

Project Partners	Country	Project Partners	Country
Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut (Coordinator)	DK	GOETEBORGS UNIVERSITET	SE
NORCE NORWEGIAN RESEARCH CENTRE AS	NO	NORSK POLAR INSTITUTT	NO
ALFRED-WEGENER-INSTITUT HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FUR POLAR- UND MEERESFORSCHUNG	DE	EUROPEAN POLAR BOARD	NL
CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR	UNITED KINGDOM RESEARCH AND INNOVATION (*)	UK
UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	NL	UNIVERSITY OF NORTHUMBRIA AT NEWCASTLE (*)	UK
ETT SPA	IT	UNIVERSITY OF SOUTHAMPTON (*)	UK
UNIVERSITE LIBRE DE BRUXELLES	BE	UNIVERSITY OF BRISTOL (*)	UK
ECOLE NORMALE SUPERIEURE	FR	THE UNIVERSITY OF READING (*)	UK
POTSDAM-INSTITUT FUR KLIMAFOLGENFORSCHUNG EV	DE		

(*) not requesting EC funding.